

P and E as Average Values in $-Et+px$ and the Question of Precision

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Classical mechanics seems to deal with limitless precision. For example, a particle may be precisely at x at t . The widths associated with these values are dx and dt , but are taken to approach 0. We argue that this view is carried over into probabilistic scenarios such as a photon moving in the x direction reflecting or refracting. Classically there is limitless precision so the photon is an incident one at one precise x and then instantaneously is either a reflected one, presumably at the same x , or a refracted one. This leads to the equation: $1 = \text{probability to reflect} + \text{probability to refract}$ ((1)), which holds for a single photon which may be written in terms of fluxes (which are average values). For this equation to make sense, one requires limitless precision so that the states (incident, reflected, refracted) are precise and exist at precise times. We argue (as we have before) that this is the inherent reason why ((1)) is not sufficient to solve for the relative probabilities of reflection/refraction. We suggest that the interaction at an n_1 - n_2 interface (indices of refraction) is complicated and there is not sharp x, t precision or even a clear picture of what is instantaneously occurring. As a result, we suggest one uses averages to try to describe the situation, with p and E being average values during the interaction. Nonrelativistically $p = mv$ and given the quantum $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, one cannot have a precise velocity, we suggest v is an average and hence p an average.

Thus impulses may be described in terms of averages as well as speeds. This is why Snell's law may be obtained using only these average values, which are taken to be precise deterministic values in classical mechanics. The blurriness of the interaction suggests there is not an instantaneous division between the incident and refracted/reflected or even the refracted/reflected photon. As a result, it is a blurry or probabilistic scenario which describes the situation probabilistically. One may note that during the interaction, p and E could be changing so these are treated as average values. Thus the idea seems to be to use average values of p and E when describing complicated interactions, but x and t probabilities governed by these average values. The question then becomes: How does one find these probabilities? We argue (as before) that a general approach is to use maximization of Shannon's entropy (subject to periodic constraints) to obtain $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$. E and p are Lagrange multipliers and so like in classical statistical theory are averages. This equilibrium approach with its blurriness in x and t , but average p and E values, allows one to describe a complicated interaction by changes in the average value e.g. the magnitude or direction of the p vector together by adding $\exp(ipx)$ for what would be normally deterministic paths.

$\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ And Maximization of Shannon's Entropy

In classical mechanics, E, t, x and p are considered to be precise values, but at the same time there are changes dE, dt, dx and dp which shrink to zero, for which one does not really know what occurs in detail. Quantum mechanics of a free particle, on the other hand, introduces the two-dimensional probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, suggesting that x and t are probabilistically distributed. Thus, constant v is only an average, but $p = mv$ (nonrelativistically) and $E = .5mv^2$, so these two must also be averages, which are classically taken to be deterministic. Even in quantum

mechanics, E and p of a free particle are taken to be deterministic, but we suggest an inherent average status. An average p in $\exp(ipx)$ governs the x probability. As a result, $\exp(ipx)$ is a somewhat approximate value in that it depends on an average p , but this is also the case in classical statistical mechanics for which the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is $P(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$. T , temperature is an average value which governs the probability.

We have suggested before that one may obtain $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ from maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to periodic constraints i.e.

Maximize $P(t) \ln\{P(t)\} + iEt P(t)$ and Maximize $P(x) \ln\{P(x)\} - ipx P(x)$ to obtain

$\exp(ipx)$ ((2a)) and $\exp(-iEt)$ ((2b))

Opposite signs appear for p and E so that the product $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ does not change if $t \rightarrow t + \text{constant}/E$ and $x \rightarrow x + \text{constant}/p$. Here, i is used to ensure periodicity. In this approach, E and p are Lagrange multipliers which suggest average values. It is suggested that average values of E and p imply distributions in t and x and so there does not exist the deterministic sharpness of averages, but rather the distributions of equilibrium.

Why is p used in $\exp(ipx)$? We argue that this average value is sufficient to describe, on average, interactions with the added probability included in x and t . Before an interaction, the particle is described by an average p and after, this p is changed either in magnitude, direction or both. An average value of x or t , however, is not always sufficient to describe an interaction, especially of a single particle, especially if the interaction involves probability. In other words, the lack of precision or blurriness of x, t leads to the notion of adding $\exp(ipx)$ probabilities for different probabilistic outcomes because these are not sharp precise events (as they seem classically). There is a lack of symmetry in the way p, E and x, t are treated. Why should this lack of symmetry exist?

To try to answer this question, we first consider the situation of Snell's law for a medium interface along the x axis at $y=0$. n_1 is the index of refraction for $y>0$ and n_2 for $y<0$. This problem is based on impulses i.e changes in momentum and speed. In fact, one does not need to use x or t at all to solve the problem. In medium n_1 , the photon has momentum p and speed c if $n_1=1$. In medium 2 it has momentum pn_2 and speed c/n_2 . There is no impulse along the x axis, so $p(x)$ i.e. the x component of p in n_1 is the same as in n_2 . In medium 2, one has a photon with $p(x) = p \sin(\theta_1)$ (measured from the y axis) and magnitude pn_2 , where p , θ_1 and n_2 are known. Thus one knows the angle of refraction. In other words, average p and speed values are sufficient to solve this problem. The reason why the speed of light is c/n_2 in the second medium is due to stochastic interactions with atoms, but an average speed and momentum are sufficient for solving the problem and x and t do not even need to be considered.

It seems that this approach to using an average p and E (as if they were deterministic) is carried over into other problems. Consider the case of a single photon moving along the x axis in a medium with n_1 hitting an interface along the y axis at $x=0$. $n_2>n_1$ is the index of refraction for $n_2>n_1$. According to the approach used for Snell's law, one should use average p, E and speeds again. A single photon may reflect or refract with different relative probabilities, but average values are treated as deterministic. In this case, the notion of at least t comes into play

because classically, at one instant in time the photon is an incident one and then at $t+dt$ with $dt \rightarrow 0$ it is either a reflected or refracted one. Thus classically there is a sharp precision. Similarly, the photon stops being an incident one at a sharp precise x value. We suggest instead blurriness occurs during the interaction. We further suggest that it is remarkable one may use average p and E values to describe the situation, but this seems to follow from the idea of a kind of equilibrium being established. We suggest there are no sharp x, t values for which the particle is an incident one.

We suggest that it is this lack of precision which leads to problems with a deterministic precise probability equation:

$$1 = \text{reflected probability} + \text{refracted probability} \quad ((3))$$

In terms of fluxes, one may write:

$$AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2 \quad ((4)) \text{ where } AA, BB, CC \text{ are the fluxes of the incident, reflected and refracted photons and } c_2 = c/n^2.$$

The incident, reflected and refracted states are considered to be sharp and precise. The photon is an incident one at time t , but then at $t+dt$, with $dt \rightarrow 0$, it is either reflected or refracted. This precision or determinism is based on the notion of average values in x and t , and we argue that these do not sufficiently describe the situation. In other words, there is no guarantee that average values are sufficient. In Snell's law, they are, but here they are not as one may see that ((4)) is one equation with two unknowns (B, C) if A is known. One might expect a second pressure balance equation, but using $E=pc$, one sees that ((4)) is the same as this equation i.e. there is a degeneracy. We suggest the fundamental problem with only considering ((4)) is that precision (based on averaging to create a kind of determinism) eliminates probabilistic information from the scenario which is critical to solving the problem.

As a result there is some uncertainty or probability in x and t for this reaction which cannot be averaged away. If one wishes to describe the single photon scenario in terms of x , in analogy with a steady flux picture, one may consider only blurriness and probabilities in x governed by the average p values. There has to be a smoothness or continuity in these probabilities, however, at $x=0$. In general, one would have no idea as to what x, t probabilities apply. The maximization of Shannon's entropy with periodic constraints, however, allows one to find an equilibrium type of probability in a general way. As a result, one needs to retain probability in x and t , although average p and E values are still fine. One may then use continuity of $\exp(ipx)$ s and p averages at $x=0$ to obtain two equations i.e.

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip_2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((5a)) \text{ and } A p \exp(ipx) - p B \exp(-ipx) = C p_2 \exp(ip_2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((5b))$$

((5a)) shows the blurriness of these unusual periodic probabilities. One does not know if the photon is an incident, reflected or refracted one. The precision of the average value classical determinism is gone. This is also the case of a photon or particle interacting with an n -slit

device. In that situation, it is also fine to use an average p value, but the interaction is complicated and does not take place at $dx \rightarrow 0$ positions. The particle may interact with both slits in accordance with its equilibrium x distribution. Thus it seems that it is the precision of average values which leads to the notion of determinism.

The Case of Spin

We have argued above that p and E should be treated as average values. The Lorentz invariant:

$$-EE + pp = m^2 c^2 \quad ((6))$$

is thus an equation representing average values. We argued in (1) that this represents a dot product and so eliminates information. If one finds a linear equation (with $E \rightarrow i\hbar \partial/\partial t$ partial and $p \rightarrow -i\hbar \partial/\partial x$), as Dirac did, which overall still satisfies ((6)), one may find more information which is at first hidden in ((6)). We note that since E and p are considered to be average values, even the spin result should also be associated with averages because $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ is still part of the solution of the Dirac equation. Thus there seem to be two issues, one is the notion of average values and the other, a loss of information.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that averages are associated with probability distributions. We also point out that what one considers to be a deterministic value, may actually be an average one. We suggest that this may be the case for p and E for a free particle or photon. In the case of a photon moving in a medium with index of refraction n , there are many stochastic interactions with atoms which change c to c/n . Thus c/n seems to be an average as does pn (momentum). These average values, however, are sufficient to derive Snell's law in a deterministic manner.

Average values, however, suggest probability distributions and sometimes the full information of the distribution may be needed. In the case of p and E , it does not seem possible to determine the associated probability distributions unless one uses the approach of classical statistical mechanics, i.e. maximization of entropy subject to a constraint. There, the Maxwell-Boltzmann probability $P(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ is based on an average value T , temperature. Using periodic boundary conditions, we suggest (as we have before) that $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ are the associated probabilities of E average and p average. These suggest a kind of blurriness in x and t based on an equilibrium approach.

Are these probabilities required to solve any problems? The blurriness in x and t is associated with specific \hbar/p and \hbar/E values and so for an n -slit system with slit separations, one would expect the blurriness to remove the classical precision of motion through one slit or the other and replace it with interactions with both slits in a probabilistic manner.

This blurriness, we argue, appears in a more indirect manner for a photon moving in the x direction which reflects or refracts when n_1 becomes n_2 at $x=0$. A probability balance equation: $1 = \text{probability to reflect} + \text{probability to refract}$ is correct, but not sufficient to solve the problem. Writing in terms of fluxes, one has: $AA/c = BB/c + CC/c$ (AA, BB, CC are incident, reflected,

refracted fluxes). We argue that an interaction is complicated and that it is already remarkable one may use p and E averages. One cannot, however, use x , t averages and pretend there is determinism and limitless precision. During an interaction, one does not know if the photon is an incident, reflected or refracted one. This coupled with the equilibrium picture of $\exp(ipx)$ suggests one should use these instead of average x, t deterministic values. One may then form two independent equations: $A\exp(ipx)+B\exp(-ipx)=C\exp(ip2x)$ at $x=0$ and $A\exp(ipx)-B\exp(ipx) = Cp^2 \exp(ip2x)$ at $x=0$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Spin, Inner Product and Lost Information (preprint, zenodo, 2023)